

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

ELECTRICAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF SINGLE-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBE

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Abstract

Metallic nanotubes, owing to their high transparency, can exhibit excellent electrical conductivity, enabling their use as nanowires or transparent electrodes in various fields of nanoelectronics and photovoltaics. Semiconductor nanotubes, with their high charge-carrier mobility, are promising materials for transistor applications. The electronic properties of single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) can be tuned by doping with electron-donor or electron-acceptor compounds. This work presents the results of separating SWCNTs according to their conductivity type. The resulting semiconductor and metallic fractions were characterized by optical spectroscopy. When the fractions were filled with copper chloride, an electron-accepting compound, changes in their optical properties were observed. The article also employs the aqueous polymer two-phase (ATPS) separation method for sorting SWCNTs by conductivity type.

Keywords: carbon, nanotubes, semiconductor, electric.

Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) are an allotrope of carbon consisting of a graphene sheet rolled into a cylindrical shape. They have unique electrical, mechanical, and optical properties, making them useful in many technological applications — nanoelectronics, optoelectronics, sensors, and energy storage systems. Nanotubes possess several properties essential for electronics. They may exhibit either semiconducting or metallic conductivity. The magnitude and type of conductivity in semiconductor nanotubes can be modified through external influences. The electrical properties of nanotubes — high electrical conductivity and good thermal conductivity — make them promising materials for nanoelectronics. The dependence of electrical properties on structure enables the formation of pn-junctions and heterojunctions within an individual nanotube. If defects in the form of pentagon and heptagon cells located at opposite ends of the diameter are

introduced into a nanotube composed of hexagonal cells, the nanotube will bend. An AFM image of the bent nanotube in contact with a quartz substrate and gold electrodes is shown in the figure. The current–voltage characteristics of the bent nanotube are nonlinear. The upper straight section (before bending) exhibits metallic conductivity; its current–voltage characteristic is linear. The conductivity of the lower and upper sections differs due to the different orientation of lattice cells relative to the nanotube axis. It is possible to obtain nanotubes containing both semiconducting and metallic sections. Such a nanotube functions as a rectifying (Schottky) diode. The AFM image of the bent nanotube on a quartz substrate (b) and the current–voltage characteristic arising at the bend (volt-ampere characteristic) are shown.

The use of SWCNT-based media in laser physics requires a detailed understanding of their optical properties. Conductivity-sorted SWCNTs enable the advantages of both semiconducting and metallic fractions to be fully utilized. Sorting SWCNTs allows tuning of their operational spectral range, which, when matched to the laser wavelength, significantly enhances quantum efficiency. Furthermore, the narrower distribution of properties in sorted SWCNTs provides superior performance compared to unsorted mixtures. In laser physics, semiconductor nanotubes used as saturable absorbers yield greater modulation depth than mixtures of SWCNTs. Conversely, pure metallic fractions can substantially improve the performance of saturable absorbers. In photoluminescence studies, the presence of metallic SWCNTs in mixed samples increases nonradiative relaxation of photoexcited states, reducing the quantum yield of semiconductor nanotubes. This study demonstrates the separation of SWCNTs by conductivity type and examines the optical properties of the resulting fractions. The aqueous polymer two-phase separation method—based on spontaneous partitioning of two immiscible polymers, polyethylene glycol (PEG) and dextran (Dx)—was used. The PEG-rich upper phase is more hydrophobic than the dextran-rich lower phase, and the hydrophobicity contrast between the phases can be tuned by adjusting polymer concentrations.

Electrophysical Properties of SWCNTs

Depending on their chirality indices, SWCNTs may exhibit either semiconducting or metallic conductivity. Their one-dimensional structure gives rise to unique physical phenomena such as Coulomb blockade and charge transport described by the Luttinger-liquid model. Metallic nanotubes, with their high transparency, can serve as nanowires or transparent electrodes in nanoelectronic and photovoltaic devices. Semiconductor nanotubes, due to their high charge-carrier mobility, are promising for transistor fabrication. The electronic properties of SWCNTs can be modified through doping with electron-donor or electron-acceptor species.

In single-walled armchair nanotubes, as in graphene, the valence and conduction bands intersect at a single point at the Fermi level. In this case, two conductive channels arise: one when the cutting line intersects the K point of the graphene Brillouin zone, and another when it intersects the K' point. Thus, an ideal armchair nanotube exhibits metallic conductivity.

$$2G_0 = \frac{4e^2}{h} \quad (1)$$

where $G_0 = 75 \mu\text{S}$ is the conductance quantum including spin degeneracy. By shifting the Fermi level, the conductivity of nanotubes can be increased as the number of conductive channels grows. Experimental studies of SWCNT conductivity [5] showed measured conductance values to be very close to theoretical predictions. This is noteworthy because defects in nanotubes would normally be expected to scatter electrons. In practice, however, scattering of charge carriers near the Fermi level is strongly [1] suppressed. Because electron states are distributed around the nanotube circumference, the influence of a defect is effectively averaged over the entire perimeter. Consequently, the larger the nanotube diameter, the less defects affect its conductivity. As a result, ballistic transport can occur in SWCNTs.

Conclusion

The article investigates field emission in conductivity-sorted single-walled carbon nanotubes. For semiconductor nanotubes, nonlinearity in current–voltage characteristics is observed due to high electrical resistance. Separating SWCNTs by conductivity allows tuning their operational spectral range, which, when matched with laser wavelength, significantly increases quantum efficiency. Furthermore, using sorted SWCNTs is advantageous due to the narrower distribution of their properties. In laser physics, using semiconductor nanotubes as saturable absorbers allows achieving greater modulation depth compared to using mixtures of SWCNTs. On the other hand, the pure metallic fraction can significantly improve the performance of saturable absorbers.

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